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ACTIVE INTERFACES – Holistic strategy to simplify standards, assessments and certification for building integrated photovoltaics

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Common methodological framework to assess energy, climate and economic impacts of BIPV

Report 1/3

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1 Introduction

«Active Interfaces» explores holistic operational strategies overcoming obstacles for large-scale advanced PV integration into urban renewal and building renovation processes. To foster widespread deployment of building integrated PV solutions (BIPV), in «Active Interfaces» the subsequent operational goals are pursued:

- Clear identification of the different relevant operational barriers at technical, spatial, design and socio-economic levels
- Development of alternative strategic approaches for BIPV in urban renewal and building renovation processes - from industrial production to implementation by end users (with optimal equilibrium between demand and supply)
- Concrete test and optimization of these new approaches for BIPV on real case studies of urban renewal processes
- Establishment of recommendations to foster the implementation practice of BIPV-solutions in Switzerland

Within «Active Interfaces», BIPV-solutions will be developed and optimized for archetypal buildings and case studies. Resulting impacts of BIPV-solutions on energy generation and consumption, greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, costs and economic viability will be assessed and compared with renewal and renovation solutions not applying BIPV solutions.

To achieve as much consistency and comparability as possible within «Active Interfaces» and among the different projects and work packages, a common assessment methodology is developed and outlined. This methodology shall be the basis for the assessment of energy, greenhouse gas and economic impacts of BIPV-solutions as well as for comparing BIPV-solutions with non-BIPV renovation options within «Active Interfaces». The common methodology aims to define notions, to prescribe common necessary assumptions and input values like energy prices, future price developments, assessment periods, impact calculation methods, system boundaries, etc. and to provide a basis for optimizing possible BIPV solutions.

The present report 1 of econcept in Project 04 of Active Interfaces is followed by the subsequent two reports:

Report 2: «Energy-policy analysis», 30.6. 2016

Report 3: «Significance of prevailing regulations, standards and labels for the deployment of BIPV», 14.12. 2017

2 Scope of the assessments of BIPV and system boundaries

The assessments of BIPV-solutions are carried out for the archetypal buildings and the case studies investigated in «Active Interfaces» (P01, P02, P04). The assessments are supposed to appraise the following impacts categories and indicators:

- **Primary energy** use of buildings renovated (indicators for primary energy use: Total primary energy use (TPE) and non-renewable primary energy use (NRPE) in [kWh/a] or in [kWh/m²a].
 - Operational primary energy consumption by the building that is renovated
 - Primary energy consumption for operation and maintenance of the BIPV related building elements and energy related building elements of the reference building during the assessment period after renovation
 - Embodied primary energy use for the renovation measures and for possible replacements of renovated building elements during the assessment period (data base for Switzerland: KBOB Bauteilkatalog)
 - If relevant: primary energy consumption for the disposal of building elements which are replaced or disposed.
- **Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions** related to operational energy consumption and to embodied energy use during the assessment period.
Indicator for GHG-emissions: CO₂ equivalent emissions [kg CO_{2eq}/m² a].
- **Life cycle costs** during the assessment period [CHF/m² a, CHF/a]: Capital costs + operational costs + maintenance costs (+ disposal costs) minus savings of energy and maintenance costs
- **UBP** (Swiss environmental impact points) for building operation, maintenance and renovation/replacement measures during the assessment period.

(Optional) **economic viability**: Return on equity, possible rent increases

2.1 Operational energy use and related GHG-emissions

2.1.1 Components of operational energy use

We assume that the assessments are carried out for entire buildings which are renovated investigating the subsequent components of operational energy use and related GHG-emissions:

- Space heating, cooling and ventilation (HVAC)
- Domestic hot water (DHW)
- Auxiliary energy use for fans, pumps, electric valves, control devices etc.

- It is suggested not to include energy use for artificial lighting, built-in common appliances (like refrigerators, elevators etc.) and plug-in appliances (if they have to be included it is suggested to do so with the help of default values if no metered values are available (the INSPIRE calculation tool would provide default values).

2.1.2 Conversion factors from energy carriers to primary energy and to GHG-emission factors

The conversion from final energy use to **primary energy** use of energy carriers and related GHG emissions is performed with the help of primary energy conversion factors (PEF) per energy carrier and energy converting system, which take into account upstream energy use for extraction, processing, transportation and distribution of the particular energy carriers. Primary energy conversion factors and GHG emission factors are determined by life cycle impact assessment. They depend on the energy conversion system and on the share and origin of the energy carriers consumed. For Switzerland primary energy conversion factors and related GHG-emission factors as well as UBP are documented in Frischknecht, Itten (2014, p. 5-8) for different energy systems (this is also the basis for such factors applied in in SIA 2032 «Embodied energy of buildings», SIA 2039 «Energy use for mobility depending on the building location» and SIA 2040 «Energy efficiency path»). According to Table 2.1 in Frischknecht, Itten (2014) the PEF, GHG emission factors and UBP relate to the energy delivered to the building (gross calorific value, H_o), including operational emissions of the energy converter in the building but not including embodied energy and corresponding emissions of the energy converter.

Primary energy conversion factors and GHG emission factors for electricity depend on the way electricity is generated and on the mix of generation technologies employed and consumed by the end users. For the assessment of «Active Interfaces» measures within building renovation, the national mix of electricity consumed is usually most appropriate (see Frischknecht, Itten, 2014: "CH-Produktionsmix", Table 2.1, p. 5) at least for determining primary energy impacts of electricity savings due to Active Interfaces measures:

Primary energy factors of electricity from the grid, Swiss consumption mix:

- Total primary energy PEF_{tot} : 3.14
- Non-renewable primary energy PEF_{nr} : 2.68; (whereby PEF_{fossil} : 0.47 and $PEF_{nuclear}$: 2.21)

GHG emission factors of electricity from the grid, Swiss consumption mix:

- CO_{2eq} : 0.038 kg CO_{2eq}/MJ or 0.137 kg CO_{2eq}/kWh

UBP of electricity from the grid, Swiss consumption mix: 105.9 UBP/MJ or 381.2 UBP/kWh

For a particular building it might be that the generation mix of the electricity consumed (and ordered) is known and different from the national mix of electricity consumed. In such cases the mix of electricity actually consumed can be applied for the assessment.

The primary energy conversion factor and the GHG emission factor of energy delivered by district heating and cooling is determined by the input share of the energy carriers to generate district heat or cold and by the corresponding primary energy factors. Thereby, electricity consumption of pumps, distribution losses and embodied energy of the heat distribution system have to be included in the factor of district heat/cold delivered to the building.

2.1.3 System boundaries for the assessment of Active Interface measures on energy use and GHG emissions

The system boundaries for the energy and GHG emissions related assessment of renovated buildings and the definition of the relevant energy flows are shown in Figure 1.

«Net delivered energy» (dashed dark blue line in Figure 1) comprises energy carriers delivered to the building minus on-site generated energy exported from the building to the grid or to a heating/cooling energy distribution system.

Figure 1 Definition of the levels and system boundaries of energy use in buildings being renovated, including on-site renewable energy generation, passive heat gains, exported energy and embodied energy for renovation measures (Kurnitski J., 2011, REHVA Task Force, supplemented by econcept)

2.1.4 System boundaries for on-site energy generation and for deployment of renewable energy

Usually the scope and the boundary for on-site generation of renewable energy is the building lot (boundary II in Figure 2, see below), while boundary III allows for the use of renewable energy delivered from off-site (e.g. biomass) into the building lot. Therefore, in Active Interfaces it is proposed to use boundary II or boundary III if the particular building uses off-site renewable energy like wood chips or pellets.

Figure 2 Overview of possible renewable supply options (Marszal A.J. et al. 2011, p. 975)

In certain situations it might be appropriate for the boundaries II and III to pool several buildings which have a common heating and/or cooling system to attain (economically) more favourable conditions for renewable energy generation and use boundary IV.

On-site generated electricity fully sold to an off-site owner of the generation unit is not accounted for this particular building (since electricity generated is allocated to the (external) owner of the system, using the building only as a basis for his generating system).

2.2 Conditioned area as functional unit

Units and target values for energy use and carbon emissions are usually expressed in **MJ/m²a** or **kWh/m²a** and **kg CO₂-equivalents per m²·a [kg CO₂eq/m²a]**. In certain cases

it might be preferable to have additionally "**person**" as functional unit since DHW and electricity use are rather depending on the number of persons than on the area [m²] of (conditioned) net or gross floor. For the sake of clarity, some definitions of floor area are given below:

Conditioned gross floor area (Energiebezugsfläche/surface de référence énergétique): Sum of the covered area of all conditioned floors of a building (including exterior and interior walls). Unconditioned rooms within the conditioned envelope are included too. Unoccupied, unheated basements, attics, garages outside the thermal envelope are excluded. In Active Interfaces the conditioned gross floor area is used as functional unit for area.

Figure 3 Illustration of **conditioned gross floor area** (left) and **net floor area** (right). Hatched areas: Non conditioned exterior gross and net floor area respectively

Conditioned net floor area:

Total conditioned floor area inside the building envelope excluding the external and internal walls and vents, shafts, stairs, (unoccupied) attics, basements, garages. The area is not reduced by moveable partition walls or other moveable furnishing (Figure 3).

For the precise definition of conditioned floor area of attic floors see SIA 416/1:2007, p. 23-24.

3 Energy, greenhouse gas, cost and economic viability assessment of BIPV-solutions within «Active Interfaces»

3.1 Future energy prices and interest/discount rates

It is proposed to perform the assessments with real prices and real interest/discount rates, not including inflation.

3.1.1 Energy prices

To adequately value the benefits and cost savings respectively of energy savings and on-site energy generation, it is necessary to assume a future energy price scenario or scenarios. History shows that it is very difficult to determine reliable and credible energy price developments. Usually it is assumed that the energy prices increase in the long run. In the short run the price volatility is much higher, upwards and downwards. For the time being low energy demand and abundant new gas reserves as well as decreasing costs of renewable electricity generation suggest that some of the future energy prices could be lower than predicted in the previous years and rather remain depressed, i.e. much rather on an oil price level of 60 – 80 CHF per 100 l heating oil than rise to 100 – 140 CHF per 100 l of heating oil as was expected until only recently or on wholesale electricity prices of 2.5 – 3.5 ct./kWh instead of 6 – 9 ct./kWh.

If future price increases are assumed, these increases are preferably supposed to be linear, since linear growth is more realistic and adequate for long term developments than exponential growth rates which tend to overestimate prices in the distant future (since rising prices will be dampened by the countervailing effects of the price increases).

Until recently it was proposed to adopt the price scenarios used in the calculation tool INSPIRE which is planned to be applied for cost, primary energy and GHG emission assessments of BIPV solutions. These prices used to be more or less in line with the fossil energy price perspectives of the IEA and the EIA. In light of the current slump of fossil energy prices and excess electricity generation on the EU level, energy prices of 2016 and development of energy prices after 2016 have been partially downward adjusted to take into account the newest energy resources' trends. Besides it is highly recommended to carry out sensitivity calculations with lower (and higher) energy prices for the coming 20-30 years.

Energy system	Unit	2016	2020	2030	2040	2050
Heating oil	CHF/kWh	0.075	0.095	0.12	0.125	0.13
Gas	CHF/kWh	0.009	0.11	0.13	0.135	0.14
Wood (1500 kWh/piled meter)	CHF/pm	80.0	105.0	125.0	140.0	145.0
	CHF/kWh	0.053	0.070	0.083	0.093	0.100
Wood chips (975 kWh/m ³ chips)	CHF/srm	47.50	56.00	73.00	84.00	91.00
	CHF/kWh	0.049	0.057	0.075	0.086	0.093
Wood pellets (5000 kWh/tonne)	CHF/ton	380	415	503	563	598
	CHF/kWh	0.076	0.083	0.101	0.113	0.120
Biogas	CHF/kWh	0.16	0.18	0.20	0.215	0.225
District heat average CH-mix	CHF/kWh	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.11
District heat defined by user	CHF/kWh	0.07	0.08	0.09	0.10	0.11
Electricity (CH-Mix)	CHF/kWh	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.23	0.24

Table 1: Energy prices 2016 and basic energy price scenario until 2050 (based on slightly downward adjusted price data in the calculation tool INSPIRE, which corresponded to a price scenario which is between the business as usual-price scenario and the new energy policy-price scenario NEP of the Swiss energy perspectives of the SFOE)

3.1.2 Valuation of on-site generated BIPV electricity:

In the current Swiss situation, determination of the value of electricity generation by BIPV depends on the way BIPV is installed and subsidized. At the moment there are two different subsidizing schemes for BIPV:

- **KEV/RPC feed-in remuneration at cost-model:** The valuation of generated electricity corresponds to the feed-in remuneration agreed on at the moment of BIPV installation.
- **Substitution of electricity which is delivered by the local provider and remuneration of excess generation fed-back into the grid (self-consumption model):** Self-consumed BIPV-electricity substitutes purchases of electricity from the local provider. Therefore, this share of BIPV production is valued at the price of such purchases (this price comprises energy costs and grid costs of the corresponding end user category). The surplus-share of electricity generation which is fed-back into the local grid substitutes electricity the local provider would have to purchase from its upstream supplier or generate itself. Therefore, this share is only remunerated either at the costs the local provider can avoid or at a price the local provider is willing to pay. At the time being the range of remuneration in Switzerland ranges between 3 and 25 ct./kWh (Fischer D., 2016).

BE Netz AG has developed a tool, for calculating the share of on-site generated PV-electricity which can be self-consumed on-site in the building. It has to be clarified under which conditions this tool can be employed.

Since the Swiss KEV-/RPC-remuneration is overbooked for the upcoming years and phased out anyway in the longer run, fed-back BIPV electricity is valued according to the principles of the current Swiss Energy Law (EnG, Art. 7, abs. 2). EnG requires to pay market related remunerations corresponding to the savings the utility can achieve due to the fed-back BIPV power.

The Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) issued guidelines regarding grid feed-in of renewable power production (SFOE/BFE 2015). For regular (not liberalized) small customers the remuneration for BIPV grid feed-in is supposed to correspond at least with the selling price of SFOE-demand scheme H4 (households, 4'500 kWh/a) minus a sales premium of 8% which is deducted from the price for H4-deliveries. According to ElCom (2016) the average price for electricity deliveries to H4-customers in 2016 is 6.71 ct./kWh. Subtracting a selling premium of 8% yields a **feed-in remuneration of 6.17 ct./kWh** for BIPV electricity. If the utility sells the added ecological value (certificate of origin) of BIPV electricity fed into the grid, the remuneration should be increased by 1.5-3 ct./kWh.

Bottom-up estimations of avoided costs for the utilities by BIPV-electricity fed-into the grid yield similar results for the remuneration: 7.36 ct./kWh, assuming a wholesale price of 3 ct./kWh and grid costs of 5 ct./kWh minus 8% selling premium for the use of the grid infrastructure from grid level 1 to the 16 kV medium-voltage level of the utility. VESE (2016) determined average feed-in remunerations of 8.09 ct./kWh for 29 kVA PV systems (228 utilities) and an average of 7.44 ct./kWh for 150 kVA systems (159 utilities). According to VESE (2016) average added ecological value is remunerated with 1.8 and 1.27 ct./kWh for 29 kVA and 150 kVA systems, respectively.

Conclusion for the valuation of fed-in BIPV electricity:

We suggest to assume at the moment a minimal remuneration for fed-in BIPV electricity of at least **6.2 ct./kWh plus at least 1.5 – 2.0 ct./kWh** for the added ecological value, if the utility can sell the added value.

3.1.3 Interest rate / discount rate

Real interest rates depend on the general time preference of the relevant actors and on the risk related to the measures assessed. Since the life time and related amortization periods of BIPV and energy related building elements are typically long, technology development is relevant and energy prices are volatile, building renovation measures and BIPV solutions can be considered as quite risky.

The guideline SIA 480 for economic assessments of buildings (SIA 480, 2004; being amended 2015) recommends for private building projects a real interest rate of 3% to 3.5% p.a. For cantonal or federal projects with assumingly less risk exposure, recommended real interest rates are 0.5% (cantonal projects) and 1% p.a. (federal projects) lower. In the current situation it is recommended to apply a real **interest rate of 3% p.a.**

3.2 Expected lifetime and amortization period of building elements

For economic assessments it is adequate to apply the expected service life for amortization of initial investments in building elements. The service life is limited either by the technical lifetime of the element or by the user, if replacement takes place before the end of the

lifetime of the particular building element. If there is no indication for a particular user dependent service life period it is recommended to use the expected lifetime of building elements according to the CRB LCC Handbook (CRB 2012) as proxy (Table 2).

Building element		Expected lifetime [years]	Amortization period [years]	
C	Building construction	(CRB LCC)	(SIA 2032)	
C 1	Bodenplatte, Fundament	base plate, foundation	75	60
C 2.1	Aussenwandkonstruktion	construction of exterior walls	80	60
C 2.2	Innenwandkonstruktion	construction of interior walls	65	60
C 3	Stützenkonstruktion	bearing structure	75	60
C 4.1	Decke	ceiling	75	60
C 4.3	Balkon	balcony	60	40
C 4.4	Dackkonstruktion	roof construction	75	60
D	Technical systems	(CRB LCC)	(SIA 2032)	
D 1	Elektroanlagen	electrical installations	45	30
	PV-Anlagen, Abnahme des solaren Ertrages um -0.3% p.a.	PV installations, assumed decrease of solar yield: -0.3% p.a.		30
D 5.2	(Allgemeine) Wärmeerzeugung	(general) heating system	20	20
	Erdsonden	ground probes	-	40
	Solarkollektoren	thermal collectors	-	20
D 5.3/5.4	Wärmeverteilung und -abgabe	heat distribution system	60	30
D 7	Lufttechnische Anlage	air ventilation system	40	30
D 8	Wasseranlage, Sanitäranlage	water and sanitary installations	30	30
E	Exterior walls	(CRB LCC)	(SIA 2032)	
E 1	Äussere Wandbekleidung unter Terrain	exterior wall in the ground	35	60
E 2.1	Äussere Beschichtung Putze/Anstriche	finery, painting	25	40
E 2.2	Aussenwärmedämmung, Kompaktfassade	exterior insulation, compact insulation	30	30
E 2.3	Hinterlüftete Fassadenbekleidung	ventilated façade	40	40
E 2.4	Fassadensysteme	façade system	50	40
E 2.5	Verkleidung Untersicht inkl. Auskragungen	soffit cladding including overhangs	35	40
E 3	Einbaute zu Aussenwand Fenster, Tür und Tor	windows, doors	35	30
F	Building roof	(CRB LCC)	(SIA 2032)	
F 1	Dachhaut	roof cladding		
F 1.1	Abdichtung unter Terrain	sealing in the ground	25	60
F 1.2	Flachdach Schutz- und Nutzschicht	flat roof, protective and use surface	25	30
F 1.3	Geneigtes Dach, ab Tragstruktur bis Eindeckung	pitched roof, from bearing structure to the roofing	40	40
F 2	Einbaute zu Dach, Dachfenster	roof mounted components, roof window	30	30
G	Building equipment	(CRB LCC)	(SIA 2032)	
G 1	Trennwand, Tür, Tor, nicht tragend	non-bearing partition walls, doors, gates	35	30
G 2	Bodenbelag	floor covering	35	30
G 3	Wandbekleidung	wall covering	30	30

	Building element		Expected lifetime [years]	Amortization period [years]
G 4	Deckenbekleidung, Verkleidungen, Putze, Platten	ceiling linings, claddings, coverings	30	30

Table 2: Expected average lifetimes according to CRB LCC Handbook 2012 and amortization periods according to SIA 2032 (SIA 2010)

3.3 Basic approach for the impact assessment of BIPV-solutions

Normally it can be assumed that BIPV-solutions are planned and assessed on the occasion of an anyway necessary renovation because of functional deficits, wear out or end of lifetime of relevant building elements or other user dependent reasons.

It can be assumed that BIPV-solutions are part of a renovation project which might comprise also further energy related and non-energy related measures. To correctly determine the impacts of BIPV-solutions assessed on costs, primary energy use, carbon emissions and economic viability, it is necessary to define a common reference renovation option as it would be carried out if BIPV would not be part of the package of renovation measures. This non-BIPV solution (Ref. 1 in Figure 4) is called the «reference renovation» option or the «anyway renovation» option. The comparison of the renovation option applying BIPV (Ref. 2 in Figure 4) with the «reference renovation» option Ref. 1 creates a level playing field for the assessment of the consequences of BIPV deployment on costs, economic viability, energy and GHG savings compared to an reference renovation option. In both cases it is supposed that the functionality of the building elements which are the trigger for the building renovation is fully restored for another life cycle of these elements, one time with BIPV and the other time without BIPV. Both solutions will provide a building which is renovated, which is supposed to be functionally viable for the next 20 years and which complies with existing energy related regulations and requirements.

Figure 4 «Reference renovation» (Ref 1) and «renovation with BIPV» (Ref 2) in the case of an anyway necessary building renovation due to functional reasons or building elements at the end of their service life. Assessments of BIPV impacts are done by comparing the impacts of a renovation with BIPV (Ref 2) with the impacts of a reference renovation (Ref 1). Thereby it is assumed that the necessary renovation has some depth and needs a building permit which is related with the requirement to comply with existing energy related requirements and regulations (which is usually not necessary for simple anyway renovations).

Definition of the reference renovation option for Active Interfaces:

- Generally speaking the reference renovation option (Ref 1 in Figure 4) is the renovation solution which would be carried out if there is no deployment of BIPV elements. If we assume that renovation projects evaluating BIPV are not just minor projects, not requiring a building permit, we suppose that the renovated building will have to comply with existing cantonal/ municipal energy performance and renewable energy deployment standards. Within Active Interfaces it is assumed that MuKEEn/MoPEEC 2014 (EnDK 2014) is the building energy standard which has to be fulfilled by new and by renovated buildings in Switzerland.

3.4 Cost assessment

The scope of cost evaluation is based on a **lifecycle cost** (LCC) approach, comprising the following cost elements (see Figure 5):

- **Global cost** meaning the sum of the present value of the initial investment costs plus the present value of the sum of running costs (energy, operational and maintenance costs), replacement costs (referred to the starting year), disposal costs (if applicable) during the calculation period or life cycle. Calculation of global costs: See Appendix.
- **Annuity:** The annuity method transforms any one-off costs (initial investment, replacement or one-off maintenance costs) to average annualized costs depending on the initial costs, the interest rate and the life time of the investment and comprising interest costs and amortisation of initial investment costs. Its application requires projections on the energy costs and the interest rates for the assessment period. Calculation of annuities: See Appendix.
- **Initial investment costs**, comprising all costs incurred up to the point when the building or building element is renovated and ready to use. Initial investment costs include costs for planning and approval, purchase of building elements, connection to suppliers, installation and commissioning processes (see Figure 5). Costs for not energy related renovation measures which are the same for the reference renovation as well as for the renovation with BIPV, can be skipped in the assessment.

To get also an owner or investor cost perspective besides the social cost perspective, subsidies and possible tax deductions have to be estimated and integrated into the cost assessment by subtracting them from the initial investment costs (the tax deductions are depending on the tax relevant income of the (private) building owner).

- **Replacement costs** during the assessment period or the remaining life span of the building: Investments during the assessment period for building elements which have to be replaced according to their economic lifecycle.
- **Running costs**, comprising:
 - **Annual energy costs**, including fixed and peak charges for energy as well as national taxes (VAT, energy and CO₂ taxes)) and costs for auxiliary energy use
 - **Operational costs**, including annual costs for insurances, utility charges and other standing charges and taxes (see Figure 5)
 - **Maintenance costs**, including annual costs for measures for preserving and restoring the desired quality of the building or building element: Annual costs for inspection, cleaning, adjustments, repair and consumable items (see Figure 5).
- **Disposal costs**: The costs for deconstruction at the end of life of a renovated building element including deconstruction, removal of building elements that have not yet come to the end of their lifetime, transport and recycling;
- **Residual value** of a building, meaning the sum of the residual values of the building or renovated building elements at the end of the calculation period;
- **Lifetime of a building**: Corresponds to the residual expected lifetime at the moment of building renovation. If the residual lifetime is unknown a building lifetime and calculation period of 60 years is assumed (for the sake of analysis);
- **Starting year** is the year in which the assessment period starts.

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Figure 5 Cost categorization into one-time costs (initial investment costs and replacement costs [CHF]) and into annual accruing costs (running energy, operational and maintenance costs; [CHF/a])

3.5 Economic viability, added value and impact on rents

3.5.1 Economic viability

From the cost perspective economic viability of BIPV solutions for the investor or building owner mainly depends on the initial investment costs and the savings of operational, maintenance and energy costs. Besides these cost and cost saving impacts economic viability and net benefits for the owner or investor depend on the following factors:

- Possible federal, cantonal and municipal subsidies and tax deductions (if not considered already in the cost assessment)
- The possible share of costs which can be passed on to the users which is depending on:
 - Current tenancy law and regulations, limiting the passing on of renovation costs for value adding measures to the users (BIPV solutions and renovation measures increasing energy performance are usually value adding). Depending on the extent of the particular renovation project and the share of value adding measures within the package of renovation measures, it can be expected that 50 – 80% of the renovation costs can be passed on to the users in case of a renovation with BIPV, in the French part of Switzerland this will be rather 50-70% and in the German part rather 70-80% (econcept/CEPE 2005a).

- Perceived added value and benefits for the users or buyers of the building: If renovation costs can be passed on to the rents or to the building price at all is not only depending on regulatory limits but also on housing demand and on the housing market situation. Passing on is only feasible if users are willing to pay the higher rents or higher building price in case of building sales.

Added building value of BIPV depends on net energy cost savings, taking into account capital costs (interest and amortisation) of energy related measures, energy and maintenance cost savings and the local remuneration for on-site generated electricity. It comprises also further benefits which might result in a higher valuation of the building by the users or buyers: E.g. higher thermal comfort, higher aesthetic quality, reduced dependence on energy deliveries and fossil energy prices, appreciation for contributing to renewable energy supply, etc. As far as added value gives rise to higher rents or higher sales prices which depends as mentioned above on the real-estate and housing market, it could be the relevant indicator to assess economic viability of BIPV renovations.

The assessment of the overall resulting economic impacts of a renovation project with BIPV is demanding, since the influence of qualitative impacts like better thermal comfort has to be included in the assessment as well as the regulatory and demand or market related framework conditions. At the very end it is the willingness to pay combined with the (legal) possibility to pass on the costs of the renovation with BIPV to the rents (or the sales price) which determine the resulting net benefit for the owner and investor. But very often information on local willingness to pay for housing is not available which is why the assessments are usually made on the cost level and not on the level of rent revenues or added value.

There are some guidelines for estimating the passing on factor for BIPV and energy related renovation measures mentioned above (see also econcept/CEPE 2005a). There are only few studies estimating willingness to pay for energy related renovation measures which could be used to estimate the appreciation of the qualitative aspects of building renovation mentioned above (e.g. econcept/CEPE 2005b; ZKB 2004).

3.5.2 Impact of building renovation with BIPV on rents

To assess the impact of building renovation on rents it is necessary to determine the resulting change of the energy bill after renovation (including possible changes in operational costs) and the amount of capital costs which is passed on to the rents (i.e. the pass on factor applied).

Capital costs comprise amortization and interest payments for the initial investment with subsidies subtracted. It has to be decided if possible tax deductions are also subtracted from initial investment costs relevant for determining capital costs and rents, meaning that tax deductions collected by the owners do shine up in the calculation of the rent. Tax deductions are economically very relevant but not transparent at all and it has to be assumed that most of the owners profiting from tax deductions do not pass on the deductions on the tenants (not least because these tax savings can actually be realized only with a delay of

1-2 years). This increases on the other hand the attractiveness of such investments for the investors or owners.

3.5.3 Individual perspective of owners/investors and societal perspective of policy makers

Economic viability of BIPV renovations depend on the perspective assumed:

- **Owner's/investor's perspective:** To assess economical attractiveness of BIPV renovations for owners, all subsidies, taxes, tax deductions and rent passing on factors have to be taken into account.
- **Societal perspective of policy makers:** Policy makers need for their policy making activities an assessment which is not distorted by subsidies, taxes and tax deductions except the VAT and taxes to internalize external effects (like energy and CO₂-taxes)

4 BIPV assessment procedure

Drawing from the previous sections, the subsequent generic assessment procedure is proposed and outlined for the teams appraising case studies and archetypal buildings.

The basic assessments are carried out for the current legal and regulatory framework conditions, not taking into account existing subsidy programs to give an undistorted view of economic viability of the solutions assessed (societal perspective). An assessment which takes into account existing subsidy and tax deduction programs can demonstrate the impacts from an owner and investor perspective. The assessments are supposed to apply as far as possible the notions, definitions and input values elaborated in this report.

Appendix

A-1 Global cost method

(Ott, Bolliger, Ritter, 2015, p. 60f.)

By applying the **global cost method**, the present value of all investment costs (initial investment costs and replacement costs during the assessment period) and of the running costs (energy, operational and maintenance costs; see Figure 5) during a predefined calculation period or during the remaining life of the building are determined. Thereby all future costs, cost savings and monetary benefits are discounted to the starting year and summarized which yields the present value of the corresponding cost and benefit flows during the assessment period.

Often buildings or certain building elements have a longer life span than the assessment period assumed. In such cases it is necessary to estimate a residual value for the building or for building elements at the end of the assessment period. To estimate residual values at the end of the assessment period, linear depreciation is used. Discounted residual values have to be added to the net present value. For the calculation period energy prices and interest rates as well as operational and maintenance costs have to be projected for every year of the evaluation period to be taken into account and discounted properly. This method corresponds with the discounted cash flow method commonly used in the realm of building development and management.

Global costs:

$$\text{Global cost } C_g(t) = C_l + \sum_k \left[\sum_{j=1}^t \left(C_{a,j}(k) \times \left(\frac{1}{1 + \frac{r}{100}} \right)^j \right) - V_{f,t}(k) \right]$$

t : Assessment period

$C_g(t)$: Global cost (referred to starting year t_0) over the calculation period

C_l : Initial investment costs for measure or set of measures k

$C_{a,j}(k)$: Annual cost during year j for measure or set of measures k

$V_{f,t}(k)$: Residual value of measure or set of measures k at the end of the calculation period (discounted to the starting year t_0)

A-2 Annuity method

(Ott, Bolliger, Ritter, 2015, p. 61f.)

The **annuity method** transforms investment costs into average annualized costs, yielding constant annual costs during the life span of the investment considered. Minimal time horizon for the assessment period is usually the service life of the building element with the longest life expectancy. Yearly energy costs, operational costs and maintenance costs are

added to yearly annuity costs of initial investment, yielding constant yearly global costs during the evaluation period. If energy prices as well as yearly operational costs and maintenance costs are not constant during the calculation period, it is necessary to determine and apply an adjustment factor¹ to take into account real future energy price increases or real future cost increases.

General average adjustment factor for price or cost increases applying the annuity method:

a annuity for constant real prices (costs)

m general average adjustment factor

t time range of cost evaluation

i real interest rate

r rate of yearly increase of energy prices, maintenance costs or operational costs

$$\text{Annuity } a: \quad a = \frac{i \cdot (1+i)^t}{(1+i)^t - 1}$$

If the energy prices or the costs are rising, it is necessary to calculate an average energy price or cost value, which dynamically takes into account the price or cost increases in the period t . This can be done by calculation of an average or medium adjustment factor m which has to be multiplied with the energy price or the annual costs at the beginning of t with prices or costs increasing annually by a rate r (e.g. 0.02 for an annual rate of 2%):

$$m = \frac{\left(1 + \frac{i-r}{1+r}\right)^t - 1}{\left(\frac{i-r}{1+r}\right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{i-r}{1+r}\right)^t} * a$$

Example:

For a real interest rate $i = 0.03$ (3% per year), price or cost increases r of 0.04 (4% per year) during the calculation period t of 20 years, the resulting average price (cost) increase factor m is:

$$m = 1.49$$

Hence yearly capital cost c for an initial investment I are:

$$c = a \cdot I$$

If yearly energy costs e are increasing by 4% p.a. and the real interest rate i is 3% p.a. the adjusted average annual energy costs e_a during period t are:

$$e_a = e \cdot m$$

The guidelines of the EPBD-recast propose to apply the global cost method.

The annuity method is favourable in the case of parametric cost assessments of various packages of renovation measures. By using the annuity method, it is not necessary to determine residual values at the end of a preset assessment period for measures which have a longer life than the assumed time horizon of the cost assessment. Hence it is easy to obtain average yearly costs (or costs/m² per year) for measures with different service lives. In the annuity method it is assumed that building elements are replaced at the end of their element-specific service life (i.e. corresponding replacement investment is taken into account).

¹ The general average adjustment factor for price or cost increases applying the annuity method

Literature

- CRB Schweizerische Zentralstelle für Baurationalisierung (2012); Handbuch LCC, Instandhaltung und Instandsetzung von Bauwerken; Zürich, 1. Auflage 2011-2012
- eco-bau, KBOB Bauteilkatalog: <http://www.bauteilkatalog.ch/ch/de/Bauteilkatalog.asp>
- econcept/CEPE; (2005a): Mobilisierung der energetischen Erneuerungspotenziale im Wohnbaubestand; commissioned by SFOE, Zürich November 2005
- econcept/CEPE; (2005b): Direkte und indirekte Zusatznutzen bei energieeffizienten Wohnbauten; commissioned by SFOE, Zürich 2005
- EICom (2016): Eidgenössische Elektrizitätskommission (Swiss Federal Electricity Commission), prices for electricity for different customer categories and regions in Switzerland: <https://www.strompreis.elcom.admin.ch/>
- Fischer D. (2016): Einspeisetarife für PV Strom gemäss EnG Art. 7: Schweizweite Übersicht der Situation in 2015 und 2016; VESE, Verband unabhängiger Energieerzeuger; presentation at the Swiss national photovoltaic conference, Berne, 22. – 23. February 2016
- Frischknecht R.; Itten R. (2014): Primärenergiefaktoren von Energiesystemen, v2.2+; commissioned by BAFU and KBOB, Uster, June 11th 2014
- Kurnitski J.; (2011): How to calculate cost optimal nearly net zero energy building performance? REHVA Journal, Oct. 2011
- Marszal A.J., Heiselberg P., Bourelle J.S., Musall E., Voss K., Napolitano A., (2011): Zero Energy Building – A review of definitions and calculation methodologies; Energy and Buildings 43 (2011) 971 - 979
- EnDK (2014), Konferenz kantonaler Energiedirektoren; MuKEEn/MoPEC 2014 Mustervorschriften der Kantone im Energiebereich 2014, 2014
- Ott W.; Bolliger R., Ritter V., (2015): Methodology for cost-effective energy and carbon emissions optimization in building renovation; commissioned by IEA EBC Annex 56 and SFOE, econcept Zürich, May 2015
- SFOE/BFE (2015): Vollzugshilfe für die Umsetzung der Anschlussbedingungen der Elektrizitätsproduktion gemäss Art. 7 und Art. 28a des Energiegesetzes (EnG; SR 730.0), January 2015
- SIA 2032 (2010): Graue Energie von Gebäuden (embodied energy of buildings); Merkblatt 2032; SIA Swiss society of engineers and architects, Zürich 2010
- SIA 380/1:2009: Thermische Energie im Hochbau (thermal energy in buildings); SIA Swiss society of engineers and architects, Zürich, 2009
- SIA 416/1:2007: Kennzahlen für die Gebäudetechnik (key indicators for building integrated technical systems); SIA Swiss society of engineers and architects, Zürich, 2007

VESE (2016), Diego Fischer, Verband unabhängiger Energieerzeuger: Einspeisetarife für PV-Strom gemäss EnG Art. 7: Schweizweite Übersicht der Situation in 2015 und 2016; 14. Nationale Photovoltaik-Tagung, 22./23. Februar 2016, Bern

ZKB Zürcher Kantonalbank; (2004): Hedonische Immobilienbewertung – Das Haus und seine Merkmale; in ZKB (editor): Preise, Mieten und Renditen; Zürich, 2004